

PRO4RS WG Final Report

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Introduction

The PRO4RS WG produced outputs to support research performing organisations worldwide to develop, align, and implement policies on research software, as a key component of FAIR and open science/scholarship. It was a joint initiative of the Research Software Alliance (ReSA) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

This report outlines the rationale for this work and its achievements, including both outputs and the engagement undertaken. This report constitutes an RDA [Supporting Output](#).

Rationale

Research software is now an important element of the research lifecycle across almost all domains. Despite this, and perhaps because the use of research software has grown organically over the last couple of decades, research institutions that have strong policies and guidance for staff around many research processes, do not have this for research software. An increasing number of initiatives are focusing on implementation of research software within the context of FAIR and open science. Efforts to align policies from funders, journals, and governments are also in progress. However, there is a significant gap around how research performing organisations can develop and implement local policies to help support sustainability of software outputs, ensure reproducibility of research outputs, and underpin research quality. The WG aimed to develop outputs to advance the ability of research performing organisations worldwide to create, share, manage, and re-use research software (a research output that is not often recognised), via policies, including use of the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) Principles.

Research software is defined in the [FAIR4RS Principles](#) as including “source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the

research process or for a research purpose. Software components (e.g., operating systems, libraries, dependencies, packages, scripts, etc.) that are used for research but were not created during or with a clear research intent should be considered software in research and not Research Software. This differentiation may vary between disciplines.”

In the context of scientific research, research data management policies were implemented 1) to encourage transparency, integrity, preservation, and the general maximisation of value of research data; and 2) in response to funder and other high-level mandates. Research software policies are closely interconnected and mutually supportive to research data management policies. Nonetheless research software is fundamentally different from research data and needs to be treated as such; it should not be seen as simply another type of data. Simultaneously, there are currently few funder and high-level mandates related to research software.

Achievements

The WG has achieved the goals set out in the September 2023 WG [case statement](#):

1. Identification of [institutional policies](#) that support research software. Software policies can cover multiple aspects of software management; namely, its development, legal, ethical and secure use, protection of intellectual property rights, interaction with user and developer communities and how research software engineering as a skill is used in hiring, evaluation and promotion
2. [Resources for supporting policy change in research institutions in practice](#) highlights the challenges that the working group is addressing and our motivation for looking at them. It then summarises a variety of existing resources relevant to different stakeholders.
3. [Analysis of existing policies to define a common framework for research software policy](#) includes identification of areas where policies are lacking, to catalyse efforts. Note that these items were originally listed as two separate outputs of two separate working groups (WGs 3 and 4) in the [case statement](#).
4. [Case studies to increase adoption of \(standardised\) policies](#). These case studies were chosen from institutions listed in the database of institutional policies: Monash University (Business School), Australia; Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Netherlands; Helmholtz Association, Germany; and Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany.

The PRO4RS WG has created a community focused on better understanding and addressing core challenges in research software, to enhance the ways that research-performing organisations recognise and support research software. The WG has engaged more than one hundred community members at public webinars and RDA plenaries, including:

- RDA Plenary 21, October 2023 ([recording](#) and [slides](#))
- [Netherlands recognition and rewards festival](#), November 2023 ([slides](#))
- RDA Plenary 22, May 2024 ([recording](#) and [slides](#))
- RDA Plenary 23, November 2024 ([recording](#) and [slides](#))
- [New Zealand Research Software Engineering Conference](#), September 2025 ([slides](#))
- RDA in NL Community meet-up, September 2025 ([slides](#))
- LA Referencia, RDA, and ReSA webinar, September 2025 ([recording](#) and [slides](#) - in Spanish)
- RDA Plenary 25, October 2025 ([slides](#))

Social media was also utilised to increase awareness of the project, crowdsource policies and resources, and to invite community members to join in sub-working groups focused on key outputs. This included ReSA and RDA communications, such as the [ReSA newsletter](#).

Community engagement included interactions with FAIRsharing, whose [policy registry](#) contributed to the identification of [institutional policies](#). Discussions are underway to expand the relationship, specifically to ensure that additional policies that the PRO4RS work has identified are deposited in the FAIRsharing policy registry. The PRO4RS WG may also make suggestions on additional metadata for incorporation into the registry, although the final decision lies with FAIRsharing due to workload reasons.

WG Summary and Methods

This section of the report summarises the work undertaken and the approaches used to develop each of the deliverables detailed in the [case statement](#). Work was carried out by a set of sub-groups (SGs), each co-led by a sub-set of the WG co-chairs, with input from group members and external entities as required.

1. Database of Research Software Policies: The database of software policies is an extension of the database already initiated by ReSA. Sub-group 1 further developed this database through a combination of crowdsourcing details of existing policies, engaging with key stakeholders and undertaking searches for relevant literature and policies online. As noted above, FAIRsharing's policy registry proved to be an important tool for identifying existing policies.

A [Google Form](#) was created to gather information on institutional policies and this was then promoted widely via a variety of approaches. Emails were sent to key groups, including national RSE networks, the form was highlighted in the ReSA newsletter and to members of the PRO4RS WG, advertisements were shared via social media channels and details of the work were presented at RDA Plenary 21 in October 2023. This activity was augmented by online search for relevant terms. A set of almost 20 search terms was identified and these terms were applied in English, Spanish and German to facilitate discovery of additional resources from online resources. Following review, assessment and collation of the discovered and submitted data, a resulting set of existing [institutional policies](#) from 12 countries was shared. Additional work enabled by RDA Tiger funding identified 80 possible additions from a much wider range of countries. This both enriched the database and resulted in the listing of other types of policies and supporting documents on the database website, to provide resources of use to a wider group of stakeholders.

2. Supportive Resources for Policy Change: Beyond policies themselves, a significant challenge is supporting and enacting policy change, especially in the research environment which has many longstanding, embedded structures. In this context, sub-group 2, worked on identifying existing resources to support policy change, publishing these and associated guidance in the report, [Resources for supporting policy change in research institutions in practice](#).

A call for contributions was prepared and shared with a set of key stakeholders identified by the sub-group leads, as well as being advertised to the PRO4RS WG members. This resulted in engagement from a small number of interested parties who joined the SG2 leads in undertaking the work of capturing, assessing and collating resources.

3. Common Framework for Research Software Policy and Report on areas where policies are lacking, to catalyse efforts: These outcomes for these two aims were combined in the report, [Identifying Gaps in Research Software Policy](#). The reports analyses 38 institutional policy documents based on their direct or indirect treatment of research software and codes them against 15 policy categories identified through community consultation. The findings show that while many institutions include research software in policies on infrastructure, licensing, or open science, few address areas concerning research assessment reform. The report concludes with a recommendation to further revisit the idea of a fixed common framework and suggest to work on a multilayered approach for policy development.

4. Case studies to increase adoption of (standardised) policies: SG5 conducted a series of interviews with research organisations that have implemented policies that support research software. These interviews capture how and why the policy was developed, to serve as inspiration to other institutions who plan to implement their own policies.

Conclusion

The PRO4RS WG has produced a range of outputs that research organisations can utilise to improve support for research software and its personnel through organisational policy. These will be shared with the research community through a range of avenues, including a session of the PRO4RS WG at the RDA Plenary 24 in October 2025, in Brisbane, Australia. This session will include discussion on how to disseminate outputs to the target stakeholders of research institutions (potentially through research consortia) to encourage adoption.

A key motivation for institutions to develop and implement these policies is compliance with funding agency, government, and disciplinary requirements and norms around data and software management. Ultimately, by establishing solid policies for research software management, institutions can promote good research practices, enhance collaboration, foster reproducibility, develop (and train) more effective researchers (both students and employees), and maximise the value to the institution and the impact of efficient and reliable scientific research. Excellence in this area can also enable institutions to achieve greater research impact than peer organisations who do not have this approach.

The database of [institutional policies](#) that support research software will continue to be updated. Community members are encouraged to continue to add to this, and to assist in disseminating the outputs of the PRO4RS WG, and encouraging their uptake in their own communities.

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